

Publisher: GSA
Journal: GEOL: Geology
DOI:10.1130/G37239.1

1 Years to weeks of seismic unrest and magmatic intrusions
2 precede monogenetic eruptions

3 **Helena Albert¹, Fidel Costa^{2,3}, and Joan Martí⁴**

4 *¹Central Geophysical Observatory, Spanish Geographic Institute (IGN), 28014, Madrid,*
5 *Spain*

6 *²Earth Observatory of Singapore, Nanyang Technological University, 639798,*
7 *Singapore, Singapore*

8 *³Asian School of the Environment, Nanyang Technological University, 639798,*
9 *Singapore, Singapore*

10 *⁴Institute of Earth Sciences Jaume Almera, CSIC, 08028, Barcelona, Spain*

11 **ABSTRACT**

12 Seismic, deformation, and gas activity (unrest) typically precedes volcanic
13 eruptions. Tracking the changes of this activity with monitoring data makes it
14 increasingly possible to successfully forecast eruptions from stratovolcanoes. However,
15 this is not the case for monogenetic volcanoes. Eruptions from these volcanoes tend to be
16 small but are particularly difficult to anticipate since they occur at unexpected locations
17 and there is very limited instrumental monitoring data. Many monogenetic volcanic fields
18 occur in high-density, populated areas and/or tourist destinations, and thus even a small
19 eruption can have a major economic and societal impact. We have gathered the available
20 instrumental data for unrest and combined it with new historical accounts of seismicity.
21 Our occurrences are mainly from high magmatic flux oceanic islands (Canary Islands,
22 Iceland, Papua New Guinea, Mexico, and Japan). We find that seismic activity may start

23 one or two years before eruption, but it intensifies approximately two or three months,
24 and one or two weeks, before the eruption. The petrological and geochemical
25 characteristics of the deposits show that multiple magma batches interacted in a
26 subvolcanic reservoir, and multiple intrusions occurred on a similar time scales to the
27 seismicity. We propose a general model for these eruptions where early dike intrusions in
28 the crust do not erupt (e.g., stalled intrusions) and make small plumbing systems, but they
29 probably are key in creating a thermal and rheological pathway for later dikes to be able
30 to reach the surface. These observations provide a conceptual framework for better
31 anticipating monogenetic eruptions in similar settings and magmatic fluxes and should
32 lead to improved strategies for mitigation of their associated hazards and risks.

33

34 **INTRODUCTION**

35 One of the main problems in quantifying the probability of an eruption in a
36 monogenetic volcanic field is the lack of monitoring data. Monogenetic fields can be
37 intermittently active for millions of years, but the magmatic processes and unrest
38 associated with eruptive episodes that form the individual volcanoes are very short
39 compared with the quiescence periods (e.g., Koulakov et al., 2015). Many of the
40 historical monogenetic eruptions have occurred before there was any instrumental
41 monitoring data, and our current knowledge is based on a few accounts of historical
42 eruptions (e.g. Baker, 1946; De la Cruz-Reyna and Yokoyama 2011; Sánchez, 2014). We
43 have done an exhaustive revision and compilation of the unrest activity (mainly
44 seismicity) of all the historical monogenetic eruptions for which we have had access (12
45 eruptions in total; Table 1). We have combined this information with the available data of

46 the zoning patterns of crystals to derive a conceptual model that integrates the time scales
47 from the crystals with the unrest seismic data, as has been done in stratovolcanoes such as
48 Mount Etna (Kahl et al., 2011), Vesuvius (Morgan et al., 2006), or Mount St. Helens
49 (Saunders et al., 2012).

50

51 **STUDIED ERUPTIONS AND PREVIOUS WORK ON MAGMATIC**

52 **PROCESSES**

53 The eruptions we have studied (Table 1) include seven in the Canary Islands
54 (Spain), two in the Michoacan-Guanajuato region of Mexico, and one each for the
55 Higashi-Izu area of Japan, the Goropu Mountains (Owen Stanley Range, Papua New
56 Guinea), and Heimaey island (Iceland) (Table 1). Geochemical and petrological studies
57 of these eruptions show that they were affected by open-system processes involving
58 multiple magmas (Klügel et al., 2000; Johnson et al., 2008; Valentine and Hirano, 2010;
59 Rowe et al., 2011; Martí et al., 2013; Longpré et al., 2014; Albert et al., 2015; Cortés et
60 al., 2015). Mixing between mafic magmas has been reported in seven of the ten cases
61 (Table 1). For the Jorullo and Paricutin (Mexico) eruptions, in addition to mixing
62 between similar magmas, upper-crustal assimilation has also proposed, and implies
63 stalling magma batches at various crustal levels (Johnson et al., 2008; Rowe et al., 2011).
64 Thus, these petrological studies suggest that these monogenetic eruptions are not driven
65 simply by dikes that travel from the mantle to the surface, but support a more complex
66 scenario of magma interactions and assimilation in subvolcanic reservoirs, and has been
67 proposed also for other systems (e.g., Németh et al., 2003; Johnson et al., 2008; Rowe et
68 al., 2011; Brenna et al., 2012; Martí et al., 2013; Longpré et al., 2014; Albert et al., 2015).

69 In addition, modeling of the zoning patterns of olivine crystals of the Siete
70 Fuentes, Fasnía and Arafo eruptions in the Canary Islands (Albert et al., 2015) shows that
71 there were several storage regions and magma mixing events that occurred approximately
72 one year, two months, and two weeks before the eruption. Similar time frames from
73 crystals have been found in the other studied eruptions of San Juan (Klügel et al., 2000),
74 Jorullo (Johnson et al., 2008) and El Hierro (Martí et al., 2013; Longpré et al., 2014).
75 Below we show that the time scales from the crystals and those of seismic unrest in these
76 monogenetic eruptions can be correlated, and thus allow us to propose a new conceptual
77 model of magma storage and migration before eruption.

78

79 **METHODS**

80 Instrumental monitoring data are available for four eruptions, but only for El
81 Hierro 2011 (Canary Islands) the data are of high quality by modern standards (López et
82 al., 2012). For the rest of the eruptions, we recorded the time series of accounts of felt
83 earthquakes in historical documents (see Table 1 and the GSA Data Repository¹). Some
84 documents give the number of seismic events, the effects on people, and buildings, and
85 sometimes an intensity value (e.g., Mercalli scale). Other reports are not detailed enough
86 to discern between intensities or to establish a detailed time series of the number of
87 seismic events. The lack of data in some periods for some eruptions could be due to the
88 lack of historical reports, not to the lack of earthquakes. We compared the time frames
89 and intensity of seismic activity between different events using a normalization of times
90 with respect to each eruption and number of events (Fig. 1).

91 We validated the use of historical earthquake accounts as a proxy for the level of
92 seismicity before an eruption by using the recent data set from the El Hierro 2011
93 eruption (www.ign.es). We compared the number of felt earthquakes before and after the
94 El Hierro 2011 eruption with the total number of monitored seismic events and geodetic
95 data (Supplementary Figure 1). We found that, in general, the evolution of felt seismicity
96 and measured seismicity agree quite well (despite changes in the instrumentation in the
97 seismic network), and hence validates our approach of using felt seismicity to compare
98 between different eruptions.

99

100 **RESULTS**

101 The seismic and felt earthquake data that we have compiled (Fig 1) show that
102 there are some common features between the eruptions. Some seismic events occur
103 between one or two years before eruption, and they are followed by calm periods.
104 Comparison of felt and instrumental seismicity, with deformation, during the El Hierro
105 eruption (Supp. Fig. 1) suggests that seismicity earlier than a few months before an
106 eruption could be, in fact, taken as background levels. However, for other cases (e.g., San
107 Juan 1949 eruption, Canary Islands), there are seismic and petrological data (see above)
108 that suggest that magmatic processes and associated unrest started earlier than a few
109 months before the eruption. The amount of seismicity strongly increases two or three
110 months before the eruption in almost all cases. These seismic crises might reflect the
111 repetitive intrusions of magma in the crust, and thus probably correspond to mid-crustal
112 stalled intrusions (Moran et al., 2011). These intrusions would stall and start to crystallize
113 due to cooling or degassing, and create a small plumbing system. The depth at which

114 these intrusions stall is difficult to constrain but some seismic and petrological data
115 suggest 5–15 km below the volcano (Klügel et al., 1997; Johnson et al., 2008; Browne et
116 al., 2010; Cerdeña et al., 2014; Cortés et al., 2015). Finally, virtually all the eruptions
117 show a sharp increase in seismic activity approximately two weeks to two days before
118 eruption, and might be related to magma migration toward the surface (Johnson et al.,
119 2008). The time frames from the seismicity we have found match with those derived for
120 the magma mixing and transport episodes derived from the crystal zoning studies (Fig.
121 1).

122

123 **DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS**

124 An intriguing aspect of the petrological and geochemical data for the eruptions we
125 studied is that open systems and mixing are prevalent, and imply that magmas coming
126 from depth are commonly intercepted by a shallower reservoir. This can be expected in
127 areas with high volcanic fluxes such as Iceland, but not in, for example, the Canary
128 Islands where eruptive fluxes are not high. The commonality of open-system processes for
129 many of these events may rather indicate that the early seismicity corresponds to stalled
130 intrusions. In other words, for the studied cases, magmas coming from depth in dikes
131 were not able to go straight to the surface, but stalled at some intermediate depth (Figs. 2a
132 and 2b). There are many parameters that control whether mafic dikes from the mantle
133 will be able to reach the surface, including magma buoyancy, thermal survival, tectonic
134 stress, or preexisting crustal discontinuities (Rubin 1995; Valentine and Gregg, 2008;
135 Rivalta et al., 2015). Our data set does not allow us to identify a precise control on each
136 of the eruptions, but the existence of a shallow plumbing system at mid-crustal levels (5–

137 15 km) may suggest that dikes separated from their sources and traveled as small batches.
138 Once at shallow depths (5–15 km), magmas can cool, probably degas and crystallize, and
139 evolve toward more differentiated compositions. Repetitive intrusions of small magma
140 batches at the same location are probably able to modify the thermal and rheological state
141 of the crust through which they pass and reside, and thus, when renewed dike intrusions
142 from depth occur, they require progressively lower energy to reach the surface and erupt
143 (Fig. 2) (Strong and Wolff, 2003).

144 Our conceptual model stems from the available compilation of seismic unrest and
145 petrology of the erupted magmas from a limited number of mainly high-flux systems
146 from oceanic islands, and it might not be universal for all monogenetic eruptions. Some
147 geochemical studies of deposits from monogenetic eruptions and their mantle xenoliths
148 (e.g., Spera, 1984; Valentine and Perry 2007) have proposed direct magma transfer from
149 the mantle to the surface. It seems plausible that monogenic eruptions from low-flux
150 continental interiors that are controlled by tectonic processes might work differently, and
151 may allow direct magma transfer from the mantle to the crust (e.g., Valentine and Perry,
152 2007). This would lead to shorter seismic unrest and thus less time to anticipate or
153 prepare for seismic events (Fig. 2c). However, detailed petrological studies of the crystal
154 cargo for such eruptions are lacking, and using bulk-rock geochemistry is difficult to
155 identify open-system processes and mixing of magmas from the same liquid line of
156 descent. Moreover, some studies of mantle xenoliths suggest magmas stalling at multiple
157 depths (Klügel et al., 1997; Klügel, 2001; Jankovics et al., 2015). Detailed petrological
158 studies (e.g., crystal zoning; Albert et al., 2015) of monogenetic eruptions coupled with
159 experiments and numerical models of dike migration should be able to test the

160 importance of repetitive intrusions in allowing mafic magmas from monogenetic eruption
161 to reach the surface.

162

163 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

164 We are grateful for discussions about seismicity and deformation with C. del
165 Fresno and L. García. T. Girona is thanked for discussion about dikes. M. Fernández de
166 Villalta is thanked for helping with the maps. M. Reid, G. Valentine, K. Németh, and an
167 anonymous reviewer provided valuable comments that helped to clarify and strengthen
168 various parts of the manuscript. We also thank the Teide National Park (Tenerife, Canary
169 Islands) for permission to access the studied sites. H. Albert was funded by the Spanish
170 Geographic Institute (IGN). This research was partially funded by the Earth Observatory
171 of Singapore (EOS) “Magma Plumbing Project”.

172 **REFERENCES CITED**

- 173 Albert, H., Costa, F., and Martí, J., 2015, Timing of magmatic processes and unrest
174 associated with mafic historical monogenetic eruptions in Tenerife Island: *Journal of*
175 *Petrology*, v. 56 p. 1945-1966, doi:10.1093/petrology/egv058.
- 176 Araña, V., and Ibarrola, E., 1973, Rhyolitic pumice in the basaltic pyroclasts from the
177 1971 eruption of Teneguía volcano, Canary Islands: *Lithos*, v. 6, p. 273–278,
178 doi:10.1016/0024-4937(73)90088-1.
- 179 Baker, G., 1946, Preliminary note on volcanic eruptions in the Goropu Mountains,
180 Southeastern Papua, during the period December, 1943, to August, 1944: *The*
181 *Journal of Geology*, v. 54, p. 19–31, doi:10.1086/625315.

- 182 Brenna, M., Cronin, S.J., Smith, I.E.M., Maas, R., and Sohn, Y.K., 2012, How small-
183 volume basaltic magmatic systems develop: A case study from the jeju island
184 volcanic field, Korea: *Journal of Petrology*, v. 53, p. 985–1018,
185 doi:10.1093/petrology/egs007.
- 186 Browne, B., Bursik, M., Deming, J., Louros, M., Martos, A., and Stine, S., 2010,
187 Eruption chronology and petrologic reconstruction of the ca. 8500 yr B.P. eruption of
188 Red Cones, southern Inyo chain, California: *Geological Society of America Bulletin*,
189 v. 122, p. 1401–1422, doi:10.1130/B30070.1.
- 190 Carreón Nieto, M.C., 2002, Un castigo divino: el volcán de Jorullo: Tzintzun: *Revista de*
191 *Estudios Históricos*, v. 35, p. 37–64.
- 192 Cerdeña, I., del Fresno, C., and Gomis Moreno, A., 2014, Seismicity patterns prior to the
193 2011 El Hierro eruption: *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America*, v. 104,
194 p. 567–575, doi:10.1785/0120130200.
- 195 Cortés, J.A., Smith, E.I., Valentine, G.A., Johnsen, R., Rasoazanamparany, C., Widom,
196 E., Sas, M., and Ruth, D., 2015, Intrinsic conditions of magma genesis at the Lunar
197 Crater Volcanic Field (Nevada), and implications for internal plumbing and magma
198 ascent: *The American Mineralogist*, v. 100, p. 396–413, doi:10.2138/am-2015-4812.
- 199 De la Cruz-Reyna, S., and Yokoyama, I., 2011, A geophysical characterization of
200 monogenetic volcanism: *Geofísica Internacional*, v. 50, p. 465–484.
- 201 Higgins, M.D., and Roberge, J., 2007, Three magmatic components in the 1973 eruption
202 of Eldfell volcano, Iceland: Evidence from plagioclase crystal size distribution
203 (CSD) and geochemistry: *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, v. 161,
204 p. 247–260, doi:10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2006.12.002.

- 205 Jankovics, M.É., Harangi, S., Németh, K., Kiss, B., and Ntaflos, T., 2015, A complex
206 magmatic system beneath the Kissomlyó monogenetic volcano (western Pannonian
207 Basin): evidence from mineral textures, zoning and chemistry: *Journal of*
208 *Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, v. 301, p. 38–55,
209 doi:10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2015.04.010.
- 210 Johnson, E.R., Wallace, P.J., Cashman, K.V., Granados, H.D., and Kent, A.J.R., 2008,
211 Magmatic volatile contents and degassing-induced crystallization at Volcán Jorullo,
212 Mexico: Implications for melt evolution and the plumbing systems of monogenetic
213 volcanoes: *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, v. 269, p. 478–487,
214 doi:10.1016/j.epsl.2008.03.004.
- 215 Kahl, M., Chakraborty, S., Costa, F., and Pompilio, M., 2011, Dynamic plumbing system
216 beneath volcanoes revealed by kinetic modeling, and the connection to monitoring
217 data: An example from Mt. Etna: *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, v. 308, p. 11–
218 22, doi:10.1016/j.epsl.2011.05.008.
- 219 Klügel, A., 2001, Prolonged reactions between harzburgite xenoliths and silica-
220 undersaturated melt: Implications for dissolution and Fe-Mg interdiffusion rates of
221 orthopyroxene: *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology*, v. 141, p. 1–14,
222 doi:10.1007/s004100000222.
- 223 Klügel, A., Hansteen, T.H., and Schmincke, H.U., 1997, Rates of magma ascent and
224 depths of magma reservoirs beneath La Palma (Canary Islands): *Terra Nova*, v. 9,
225 p. 117–121, doi:10.1046/j.1365-3121.1997.d01-15.x.
- 226 Klügel, A., Hoernle, K.A., Schmincke, H.-U., and White, J.D.L., 2000, The chemically
227 zoned 1949 eruption on La Palma (Canary Islands): Petrologic evolution and magma

- 228 supply dynamics of a rift zone eruption: *Journal of Geophysical Research*, v. 105,
229 p. 5997–6016, doi:10.1029/1999JB900334.
- 230 Koulakov, I., El Khrepy, S., Al-Arifi, N., Kuznetsov, P., and Kasatkina, E., 2015,
231 Structural cause of a missed eruption in the Harrat Lunayyir basaltic field (Saudi
232 Arabia) in 2009: *Geology*, v. 43, p. 395–398, doi:10.1130/G36271.1.
- 233 Longpré, M.A., Klügel, A., Diehl, A., and Stix, J., 2014, Mixing in mantle magma
234 reservoirs prior to and during the 2011–2012 eruption at El Hierro, Canary Islands:
235 *Geology*, v. 42, p. 315–318, doi:10.1130/G35165.1.
- 236 López, C., et al., 2012, Monitoring the volcanic unrest of El Hierro (Canary Islands)
237 before the onset of the 2011–2012 submarine eruption: *Geophysical Research*
238 *Letters*, v. 39, p. 1–7, doi:10.1029/2012GL051846.
- 239 Martí, J., Castro, A., Rodríguez, C., Costa, F., Carrasquilla, S., Pedreira, R., and Bolos,
240 X., 2013, Correlation of magma evolution and geophysical monitoring during the
241 2011–2012 El Hierro (Canary Islands) submarine eruption: *Journal of Petrology*,
242 v. 54, p. 1349–1373, doi:10.1093/petrology/egt014.
- 243 Mattsson, H.B., and Oskarsson, N., 2005, Petrogenesis of alkaline basalts at the tip of a
244 propagating rift: Evidence from the Heimaey volcanic centre, south Iceland: *Journal*
245 *of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, v. 147, p. 245–267,
246 doi:10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2005.04.004.
- 247 Moran, S.C., Newhall, C., and Roman, D.C., 2011, Failed magmatic eruptions: Late-
248 stage cessation of magma ascent: *Bulletin of Volcanology*, v. 73, p. 115–122,
249 doi:10.1007/s00445-010-0444-x.

- 250 Morgan, D.J., Blake, S., Rogers, N.M., De Vivo, B., Rolandi, G., and Davidson, J.P.,
251 2006, Magma chamber recharge at Vesuvius in the century prior to the eruption of
252 A.D. 79: *Geology*, v. 34, p. 845–848, doi:10.1130/G22604.1.
- 253 Németh, K., White, J.D.L., Reay, A., and Martin, U., 2003, Compositional variation
254 during monogenetic volcano growth and its implications for magma supply to
255 continental volcanic fields: *Journal of the Geological Society*, v. 160, p. 523–530,
256 doi:10.1144/0016-764902-131.
- 257 Rivalta, E., Taisne, B., Bungler, P., and Katz, R.F., 2015, A review of mechanical models
258 of dike propagation: Schools of thought, results and future directions:
259 *Tectonophysics*, v. 638, p. 1–42, doi:10.1016/j.tecto.2014.10.003.
- 260 Rowe, M.C., Peate, D.W., and Peate, I.U., 2011, An investigation into the nature of the
261 magmatic plumbing system at Parícutin Volcano, Mexico: *Journal of Petrology*,
262 v. 52, p. 2187–2220, doi:10.1093/petrology/egr044.
- 263 Rubin, A.M., 1995, Propagation of magma filled-cracks: *Annual Review of Earth and*
264 *Planetary Sciences*, v. 23, p. 287–336, doi:10.1146/annurev.ea.23.050195.001443.
- 265 Sánchez, C., 2014, *Revisión del catálogo sísmico de las Islas Canarias*: Madrid,
266 Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.
- 267 Saunders, K., Blundy, J., Dohmen, R., and Cashman, K., 2012, Linking petrology and
268 seismology at an active volcano: *Science*, v. 336, p. 1023–1027,
269 doi:10.1126/science.1220066.
- 270 Spera, F.J., 1984, Carbon dioxide in petrogenesis III: Role of volatiles in the ascent of
271 alkaline magma with special reference to xenolith-bearing mafic lavas: *Contributions*
272 *to Mineralogy and Petrology*, v. 88, p. 217–232, doi:10.1007/BF00380167.

- 273 Strong, M., and Wolff, J., 2003, Compositional variations within scoria cones: *Geology*,
274 v. 31, p. 143–146, doi:10.1130/0091-7613(2003)031<0143:CVWSC>2.0.CO;2.
- 275 Thorarinsson, S., Steinthórsson, S., Einarsson, T., Kristmannsdóttir, H., and Oskarsson,
276 N., 1973, The Eruption on Heimaey, Iceland: *Nature*, v. 241, p. 372–375,
277 doi:10.1038/241372a0.
- 278 Ukawa, M., 1993, Excitation mechanism of large-amplitude volcanic tremor associated
279 with the 1989 Ito-oki submarine eruption, central Japan: *Journal of Volcanology and*
280 *Geothermal Research*, v. 55, p. 33–50, doi:10.1016/0377-0273(93)90088-9.
- 281 Valentine, G.a., and Hirano, N., 2010, Mechanisms of low-flux intraplate volcanic
282 fields—Basin and Range (North America) and northwest Pacific Ocean: *Geology*,
283 v. 38, p. 55–58, doi:10.1130/G30427.1.
- 284 Valentine, G.A., and Gregg, T.K.P., 2008, Continental basaltic volcanoes - Processes and
285 problems: *Journal of Volcanology and Geothermal Research*, v. 177, p. 857–873,
286 doi:10.1016/j.jvolgeores.2008.01.050.
- 287 Valentine, G.A., and Perry, F.V., 2007, Tectonically controlled, time-predictable basaltic
288 volcanism from a lithospheric mantle source (central Basin and Range Province,
289 USA): *Earth and Planetary Science Letters*, v. 261, p. 201–216,
290 doi:10.1016/j.epsl.2007.06.029.
- 291 Yokoyama, I., and De la Cruz-Reyna, S., 1990, Precursory earthquakes of the 1943
292 eruption of Parícutin volcano, Michoacán, Mexico: *Journal of Volcanology and*
293 *Geothermal Research*, v. 44, p. 265–281, doi:10.1016/0377-0273(90)90021-7.

294 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

295 Figure 1. Pre-eruptive unrest in historical monogenetic volcanoes and calculated
296 mixing/intrusion times. The eruption is shown as a black line at time = 0. Red dashed
297 lines indicate 90 and 15 days prior to the eruption. Gray areas correspond to 90 days
298 before the eruption. A: Comparison between historical account (triangles) and monitored
299 data (dots) showing the days with felt earthquakes. Generally, the seismicity trend
300 changes approximately two or three months, and one or two weeks, before the eruption.
301 Inset shows a zoom view of the gray area of the main figure. Siete Fuentes, Fasnía and
302 Arafo (SF,F,A: light blue triangles); Chinyero (CH: dark pink triangles); San Juan (SJ:
303 dark blue triangles); Teneguía (T: purple triangles); El Hierro (EH: orange dots); Jorullo
304 (J: yellow triangles); Paricutín (P: green dots); Ito-oki (IO: gray dots). Details of the
305 seismicity are given in the Data Repository (see footnote 1). B: Calculated mixing times
306 for the available eruptions. Times from San Juan eruption are only approximated (dashed
307 lines). The data sources for this figure are reported in Table 1 and Data Repository.

308

309 Figure 2. Possible plumbing system configuration and evolution of events that may occur
310 below monogenetic volcanoes (schematic and not to scale). The depth of the subvolcanic
311 system may vary from 5–15 km. The depth of the magma source is also variable but is at
312 least 20 km. A: Intrusion of magma approximately one or two years prior to the eruption,
313 stalling of magma at 5–15 km due to the loss of buoyancy or freezing of dikes, and
314 mixing processes registered by the crystals. Crustal assimilation occurs in some cases.
315 Seismic activity is felt by the population in some cases. B: Renewal of magma intrusion,
316 progressive opening of the path between deep and shallow reservoirs, and mixing
317 processes registered by the crystals. Crustal assimilation occurs in some cases. The

318 seismic activity is commonly felt by the population. C: Continued intrusion of mafic
319 magma leads to easier transfer from deep to shallow reservoirs, and this allows the
320 magma to finally erupt. Magma mixing (and crustal assimilation in some cases) are
321 recorded by the crystals. Seismicity is felt by the population. Also shown the possibility
322 that magma is directly transfer from the mantle to the surface.

323

324 ¹GSA Data Repository item 2016xxx, **[[Need names and descriptions of Data**
325 **Repository files/items here]]**, is available online at
326 www.geosociety.org/pubs/ft2016.htm, or on request from editing@geosociety.org or
327 Documents Secretary, GSA, P.O. Box 9140, Boulder, CO 80301, USA.

328

329
 330

TABLE 1. UNREST ACTIVITY AND TIMING OF MAGMATIC PROCESSES

Eruption	Location	Date (A.D.)	Magma mixing or assimilation, and ascent times	Unrest activity
SF, F, A*	Tenerife (Canaries)	1704–1705	1 year 2 months 2 weeks	1 week–1 month [†]
CH [§]	Tenerife (Canaries)	1909	Yes	2 years [†] 2–3 months [†]
SJ [#]	La Palma (Canaries)	1949	Years Few months Days	2.5 years [†] 90 days [†] 3 days [†]
T**	La Palma (Canaries)	1971	Yes	Weeks–months [†] 6 days [†]
EH ^{††}	El Hierro (Canaries)	2011	1 month/25–150 days 3 weeks/2–90days	4–5 years ^{§§} 3 months ^{§§} 1 month ^{§§}
J ^{##}	Michoacan (Mexico)	1759	10–200 days	5 months [†] 3 months [†]
P***	Michoacan (Mexico)	1943	Yes	2 months ^{§§} Weeks ^{§§}
G ^{†††}	Goropu Mountains (Papua)	1943	Unknown	2 years [†] 2–3 months [†] (?)
E ^{§§§}	Heimaey (Iceland)	1973	Yes	2 days ^{§§} 1 day ^{§§}
IO ^{###}	Higashi-Izu (Izu Peninsula, Japan)	1989	Unknown	2 weeks ^{§§} 9 days ^{§§}

*SF—Siete Fuentes, F—Fasnia, A—Arafo. Petrological data from Albert et al. (2015). Unrest data from Sánchez (2014).
[†]—Seismic historical accounts.

[§]CH—Chinyero. Petrological data in this study (see the Data Repository [see text footnote 1]). Unrest data from Sánchez (2014).

[#]SJ—San Juan. Petrological data from Klügel et al. (2000). Unrest data from Sánchez (2014).

**T—Teneguía. Petrological data from Araña and Ibarrola (1973). Unrest data from Klügel et al. (1997) and Sánchez (2014).

^{††}EH—El Hierro. Petrological data from Martí et al. (2013) and Longpré et al. (2014). Unrest data from Instituto Geográfico Nacional (www.ign.es).

^{§§}—Monitored seismicity.

^{##}J—Jorullo. Petrological data from Johnson et al. (2008). Unrest data from Yokoyama and De la Cruz-Reyna (1990), Carreón Nieto (2002) and De la Cruz-Reyna and Yokoyama (2011).

^{***}P—Parícutín. Petrological data from Rowe et al. (2011). Unrest data from Yokoyama and De la Cruz-Reyna (1990).

^{†††}G—Goropu. Unrest data from Baker (1946).

^{§§§}E—Eldfell. Petrological data from Mattsson and Oskarsson (2005) and Higgins and Roberge (2007). Unrest data from Thorarinsson et al. (1973).

^{###}IO—Ito-oki. Unrest data from Ukawa (1993).

331
 332
 333
 334
 335
 336
 337
 338
 339
 340
 341
 342
 343
 344
 345
 346

Albert, Costa and Martí. Figure 1. (.eps)

Albert, Costa and Martí. Figure 2. (.eps)

1 DETAILS OF THE SEISMICITY AND BRIEF PETROLOGICAL REVIEW

2 Canary Islands (Spain)

3 Mafic monogenetic volcanoes are common in the Canary Islands and the volcanic historical activity
4 consists of mafic and monogenetic eruptions. In 1492, during his first trip to America, Christopher
5 Columbus described the eruption of Boca Cangrejo in Tenerife which is considered the first historical
6 eruption in the archipelago (Carracedo et al, 2007). We have considered here for comparison seven
7 representative monogenetic eruptions occurred after the Boca Cangrejo eruption in the islands of Tenerife
8 (Siete Fuentes, Fasnía and Arafo in 1704-05 and Chinyero in 1909), La Palma (San Juan in 1949 and
9 Teneguía in 1971), and El Hierro (the 2011 submarine eruption) (Fig. 1a). Only the 2011 submarine eruption
10 on El Hierro has been monitored.

11 According to the information recorded in historical documents about the unrest of the eruptions of
12 Siete Fuentes, Fasnía and Arafo (1704-05) (Sánchez, 2014), the seismic activity started one week before the
13 first eruption (Supplementary Table 1). We can't establish the beginning of the unrest for the second and the
14 third eruption separately. Then, we have considered in Fig. 1a the beginning of the Arafo eruption as time =
15 0. We have recently performed diffusion modelling in olivine crystals (Albert et al., 2015) that reveals the
16 occurrence of three magma mixing processes around one year, two months and two weeks prior to the
17 eruptions (Fig. 1b).

18 The San Juan eruption occurred in 1949 in La Palma involved three eruptive centres: Llano del
19 Banco, Duraznero and Hoyo Negro (Bonelli Rubio, 1950; Klügel et al., 2000; Romero-Ortiz, 1951). Around
20 two years before the eruption two earthquakes were felt by the population and during the three months prior
21 to the eruption earthquakes became more frequent and stronger (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Table 2). A
22 previous mixing time scales study (Klügel et al., 2000) reveals the occurrence of three magma mixing events
23 some years, few months and some days before the eruption (Fig. 1b). These data match with the factual
24 accounts about the unrest activity (Fig. 1).

25 Weeks to months before the Teneguía eruption periodic earthquakes were felt by the population
26 (Klügel et al., 1997), and from six days prior to the eruption earthquakes and their intensities were reported
27 daily (Sánchez, 2014) (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Table 3). For Teneguía eruption petrological studies
28 indicate the presence of rhyolitic and basaltic magmas that coexisting and thus indicate the presence of open
29 system and subvolcanic reservoir (Araña and Ibarrola, 1973).

30 The eruption of Chinyero in 1909 was preceded by two years of seismic swarms (Sánchez, 2014)
31 (Fig. 1a and Supplementary Table 4). Our petrological study of this eruption reveals a virtually closed
32 system origin for the magmas (equilibrium textures), but with some high Mg/Fe olivine xenocryst. Thus, this
33 eruption also shows evidence of open system processes although are less well developed than in other
34 eruptions from Tenerife.

35 The last monogenetic eruption in the Canaries occurred on October 10, 2011 in El Hierro Island.
36 After a long period of quiescence in El Hierro the number of earthquakes started to increase in 2006.

37 Nevertheless during the period 2006-2010 just one earthquake was recorded as felt by the population in
38 2007. A bigger increase of the seismic activity occurred during the previous three months before the
39 eruption. During the previous month earthquakes were felt daily (Fig. 1a) (for a complete catalogue of the
40 seismic activity see www.ign.es). Diffusion times calculated from olivine crystals reveal the existence of
41 two mixing events before the eruption. There are data from two different studies. The first mixing event
42 happened between 25 to 150 days (Longpré et al., 2014) or one month prior to the eruption (Martí et al.,
43 2013), and the second event 2 to 90 days (Longpré et al., 2014) or three weeks (Martí et al., 2013) before the
44 eruption (Fig. 1b).

46 **Michoacan monogenetic volcanic field (Mexico)**

47 During the previous two months before the eruption of the Paricutin (February 20, 1943) earthquakes
48 with $M \geq 3$ were recorded by the Tacubaya seismic station (in Mexico City, 320 km away from Paricutin)
49 (Yokoyama and De la Cruz-Reyna, 1990) (Fig. 1a). Traditionally this eruption was described as a classic
50 example of fractional crystallization and crustal assimilation, and recent data have proved the existence of
51 mixing processes between three compositionally distinct magmas at shallow depth (Rowe et al., 2011).

52 Information about Jorullo unrest previous to the September 29, 1759 eruption is vague. It seems that,
53 from April some weak earthquakes were felt in the surrounding area and from the end of June every day
54 were felt between 12 and 47 earthquakes (Yokoyama and De la Cruz-Reyna, 1990; Carreón, 2001; De la
55 Cruz-Reyna and Yokoyama, 2011) (Fig. 1a). The presence of zoned olivine crystals have been related with
56 the mixing between magmas previously stalled at different levels of the plumbing system (Johnson et al.,
57 2008).

59 **Higashi-Izu monogenetic volcanic field (Japan)**

60 Based on previous works we can establish an unrest duration of two weeks with a change in the trend
61 nine days before the eruption (Ukawa, 1993) for the Ito-oki submarine eruption (July 13, 1989). In the
62 available dataset of the unrest at the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) the number of earthquakes is
63 given in time intervals. Therefore, it is not possible for us to reconstruct a proper time series to compare the
64 unrest data of this eruption before 13 days prior to the eruption in Fig. 1a. There are petrological studies that
65 also report the co-existence of mafic and silicic melts, but in this case the silicic melts were interpreted to be
66 due to melting of shallow sediments (Yamamoto et al., 1991).

68 **Goropu Mountains (Owen Stanley Range, Papua)**

69 The eruption occurred in December 1943 in the Waiowa or Goropu area was preceded by two years
70 of earthquakes, sometimes at the rate of two or three per day. Columns of steam and ash from other vents
71 were observed since October (Baker, 1946). The information is too vague to be included in Fig. 1a. We did
72 not find any petrological information.

73

74 **Heimaey (Iceland)**

75 In 1973, after two days of earthquakes (not felt by the population) and one day with shallower
76 earthquakes (three felt by the population) a monogenetic volcano (Eldfell eruption) appeared in the island of
77 Heimaey (Thorarinsson et al., 1973). Recent studies have shown evidences of mixing between magmas from
78 the same source (Mattsson and Oskarsson, 2005; Higgins and Roberge, 2007).

79

80 **REFERENCES**

81 Bonelli Rubio, J.M., 1950, Contribución al estudio de la erupción del volcán del Nambroque o San Juan
82 (Isla de la Palma), 24 de Junio - 4 de Agosto de 1949: Madrid, Instituto Geografico y Catastral.

83 Carracedo, J.C., Rodríguez Badiola, E., Pérez Torrado, F.J., Hansen, A., Rodríguez González, A., Scaillet,
84 S., Guillou, H., Paterne, M., Fra Paleo, U., and Paris, R., 2007, La Erupción que Cristobal Colón vio en
85 La Isla de Tenerife (Islas Canarias): Geogaceta, v. 41, p. 39–42.

86 Romero-Ortiz, J., 1951, La erupción del Nambroque en la Isla de La Palma. Boletín Instituto Geológico y
87 Minero, España, v. 63, p. 1–165.

88 Yamamoto, T., Soya, T., Suto, S., Uto, K., Takada, A., Sakaguchi, K., and Ono, K., 1991, The 1989
89 submarine eruption off eastern Izu Peninsula, Japan: ejecta and eruption mechanisms: Bulletin of
90 Volcanology, v. 53, p. 301–308, doi: 10.1007/BF00414526.

91

92

93

94 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

95 Supplementary Figure 1. Comparison between macroseismicity and monitored seismicity and deformation at
96 the El Hierro (Canary Islands) 2011 eruptive vent. Cumulative percent of the days with felt earthquakes
97 (orange dots) and total number of seismic events (gray dots) occurred before and after the El Hierro 2011
98 eruption. Gray line shows the vertical displacement recorded by one GPS station. Black dotted lines indicate
99 the five post-eruptive episodes of unrest. Black line at time = 0 is the eruption time. Red dashed lines mark
100 90 and 15 days before the eruption. The general trend and the abrupt changes for the three curves are
101 consistent. Note that the seismic unrest can be considered to start when deformation starts, and thus earlier
102 earthquakes can be taken as background seismicity. Note also that in July 2011, the number of seismic
103 stations at El Hierro increased from two to seven, shown by a star (Cerdeña et al., 2014). The sharper change
104 in the trend of the instrumental seismicity occurs before the felt seismicity. This is an artifact of the

105 increased in seismic monitoring, since this discrepancy is not present for the post-eruptive seismic crises.
106 The trend of the cumulative percent of days with felt earthquakes is consistent with the trend of the
107 cumulative percent of earthquakes and the geodetic data.

108

109 Supplementary Figure 2. Localities where the seismicity was felt by the population during the unrest of the
110 eruptions of San Juan (SJ, 1949) and Teneguía (T, 1971), both in La Palma, and Siete Fuentes (SF, 1704),
111 Fasnía (F, 1705), Arafo (A, 1705) and Chinyero (CH, 1909) in the island of Tenerife.

112

113 Supplementary Figure 3. Global location map. Tenerife, Canarias (Latitude 28.271°N, Longitude
114 16.641°W). La Palma, Canarias (Latitude 28.57°N, Longitude 17.83°W). El Hierro, Canarias (Latitude
115 27.73°N, Longitude 18.03°W). Michoacan, Mexico (Latitude 19.85°N, Longitude 101.75°W). Goropu
116 Mountains, Papua (Latitude 9.57°N, Longitude 149.075°W). Heimaey, Iceland (Latitude 63.43°N,
117 Longitude 20.28°W). Higashi-Izu, Japan (Latitude 34.9°N, Longitude 139.098°W).

118

Supplementary Table 1. Factual accounts of the unrest activity preceding the eruptions of Siete Fuetnes (SF), Fasnía (F) and Arafo (A).

Chronological range	Days before and after the eruption			Event	Localities	
	SF	F	A			
1704	December					
	24	-7	-12	-40	Low but continuous ground shaking. 29 earthquakes 3 h. Panic-stricken people. Houses shaken. The population leaves the houses.	LO, PC, LR
	25	-6	-11	-39	Increase of ground shaking. 23 earthquakes before the afternoon (some of them strong). Panic-stricken people. Houses shaken. The population leaves the houses.	G, C, A
	26	-5	-10	-38	Earthquakes every 2 or 3 h (some of them strong).	LO, PC, LR, G, C, A
	27	-4	-9	-37	Earthquakes every 2 or 3 h (some of them strong). Three in 1 h. Houses shaken, panic-stricken people. People realize that seismicity might be due to a volcano. Innumerable earthquakes during the night. The population sleeps outdoors.	LO, PC, LR, G, C, A
	28	-3	-8	-36	Some earthquakes, some of them strong. Some houses damaged. Panic-stricken people, especially in La Orotava.	LO, PC, LR
	29-30	-1	-6	-34	Some earthquakes, mainly small.	LO, PC, LR
	31	0	-5	-33	Some earthquakes. SIETE FUENTES ERUPTION.	LO, PC, LR
1705	January					
	2	2	-3	-31	Six strong earthquakes and some small ones.	LO, PC, LR
	3	3	-2	-30	Small earthquakes. Also the volcanic activity reduces.	LO, PC, LR
	4	4	-1	-29	Earthquakes every hour.	LO, PC, LR
	5	5	0	-28	Two very strong earthquakes in 5 h. Collapses in cliffs and mountains. Panic-stricken people. Houses strongly shaken and damaged (many collapsed). The population sleeps outdoors. FASNIA ERUPTION. (End SIETE FUENTES ERUPTION?).	LO
	8-10	10	5	-23	Many earthquakes, some of them strong. Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR
	11	11	6	-22	Many earthquakes. Four strong. Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR
	12	12	7	-21	Many earthquakes, one very strong. Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR
	13	13	8	-20	Four earthquakes in 1 h. Two earthquakes very strong in the afternoon. The population thinks another vent has opened. Continuous ground shaking. One earthquake at midnight very strong and long. Some earthquakes during the night.	LO, PC, LR
	14-15	15	10	-18	Many earthquakes. (End FASNIA ERUPTION?)	LO, PC, LR
	16	16	11	-17	(End FASNIA ERUPTION?)	
	17	17	12	-16	One earthquake very strong and long. Collapse of some houses. Panic-stricken people. Strongest effects in La Orotava.	LO
	19	19	14	-14	Many small earthquakes and some strong. One earthquake very strong.	LO, PC, LR
	20	20	15	-13	Many small earthquakes and some strong. One earthquake very strong and long.	LO, PC, LR
	21	21	16	-12	Many small earthquakes and some strong. One of the stronger earthquakes until this date. So many strong earthquakes during the night that they were not counted. The population sleeps in the churches.	LO, PC, LR
	22	22	17	-11	20 strong and smaller earthquakes. Two earthquakes very strong in 2 h. Continuous ground shaking during the night.	LO, PC, LR

	23	23	18	-10	Some small earthquakes.	LO, PC, LR
	24	24	19	-9	Many small earthquakes and some strong. Two earthquakes very strong in the morning. In the afternoon one earthquake very strong: collapse of many houses. Collapses in some cliffs and mountains.	LO, PC, LR
	25	25	20	-8	Some small earthquakes. Loud noise in the mountains and smoking areas. Some collapses in cliffs and mountains. People expect another eruption.	LO, PC, LR
1705	26-27	27	22	-6	Some small earthquakes.	LO, PC, LR
	28	28	23	-5	Many earthquakes. Two of the strongest and longest earthquakes in the morning. Other earthquakes very strong during the night.	LO, PC, LR
	29	29	24	-4	Many strong and long earthquakes (so many that they could not be counted). Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR
	30	30	25	-3	Many strong and long earthquakes (so many that they could not be counted). Continuous ground shaking. Large smoking cavity opened close to Güimar, loud noise from it. People expect a new volcano.	LO, PC, LR
	31	31	26	-2	Many strong earthquakes. Panic-stricken people. The population sleeps outdoors.	LO, PC, LR
1705	February					
	1	32	27	-1	Conflicting reports.	
	2	33	28	0	Many strong earthquakes. Houses shaken (collapse of some buildings). People fall down because of the ground shaking. Panic-stricken people. People expect a new volcano. Very strong earthquake felt in the upper valley between Güimar and Arafo. ARAFO ERUPTION.	LO, PC, LR
	3	34	29	1	Two strong earthquakes felt in the whole island. Collapse of some houses. People relate these earthquakes to the opening of a new vent in the volcano. People fall down because of the ground shaking. Panic-stricken people. Collapses in cliffs and mountains.	LO, PC, LR
	4-28	59	54	26	Seismic activity continues.	LO, PC, LR
1705	March					
	1-27	86	81	53	Seismic activity continues. End of ARAFO ERUPTION on March 27th.	

LO, La Orotava; PC, Puerto de la Cruz; LR, Los Realejos; A, Arafo; C, Candelaria; G, Güimar (Supplementary Figure 2).

121
122
123
124
125
126
127
128
129
130
131
132
133
134

Supplementary Table 2. Factual accounts of the unrest activity preceding the eruption of San Juan.

Chronological range	Days before eruption count down	Event	Localities
1947 January			
22	-883	One earthquake.	EP
May			
6	-779	One earthquake.	EP
1949 March			
24	-91	Cracks in the lighthouse of Fuencaliente. From this day earthquakes become more frequent and stronger.	EP
1949 June			
20	-3	Two strong earthquakes.	EP
22	-1	Frequent small earthquakes. People with restlessness.	EP
23	0	Small earthquakes felt in the whole island, but stronger in Las Breñas, Mazo and the Valle de Aridane. No damages. SAN JUAN ERUPTION.	LB, M, VA, EP, LLN, LM, J, F
1949 July			
29	36	End SAN JUAN ERUPTION.	

EP, El Paso; LB, Las Breñas; M, Mazo; VA, Valle de Aridane; LLN, Los Llanos; LM, Las Manchas; J, Jedey; F, Fuencaliente (Supplementary Figure 2).

135

Supplementary Table 3. Factual accounts of the unrest activity preceding the eruption of Teneguía.

Chronological range	Days before eruption count down	Event	Localities	Maximum Intensity
1971 October				
19	-6	One small earthquake. Vibration of furniture in the houses.	F	
20	-5	Six or seven earthquakes (three stronger compared to the others) felt in the area between Fuencaliente and Valle de Aridane. No damages.	F, VA, M, EP	III (EMS-98)
21	-4	13 earthquakes, four of them strong. Some people sleep outdoors in El Paso and Fuencaliente. According to the Newspaper "Diario de Avisos", almost 100 seismic movements with different intensities were recorded in Fuencaliente. 1000 seismic events recorded by the hydrophonic station of the Palisade Geophysical Institute in Puerto Naos (La Palma).	F, VA, M, LLN, EP	II (EMS-98)
22	-3	15 earthquakes, at least four strong during the night. Population feel great fear and leave the houses. During the day one strong earthquake trigger collapses in cliffs and mountains and landslides blocking coast roads in the Fuencaliente area. Las Indias hermitage bells tolled alone.	F, VA, M, LLN, EP	III (EMS-98)
23	-2	Four small earthquakes.	F	
24	-1	One strong earthquake (the strongest until this day) of 12-16 s and five small earthquakes. Las Indias hermitage bells tolled alone. Collapses in cliffs and mountains and landslides. Damages in walls and roofs of some houses. Population feel great fear and leave the houses. The earthquake was felt even in the north of the island.	F, VA, SA, S, SC	IV (EMS-98)
25	0	TENEGUIA ERUPTION.		
1971 November				
17	23	End TENEGUIA ERUPTION.		

F, Fuencaliente; VA, Valle de Aridane; M, Mazo; EP, El Paso; LLN; Los Llanos; SA, San Andrés; S, Suaces; SC, Santa Cruz (Supplementary Figure 2).

136

Supplementary Table 4. Factual accounts of the unrest activity preceding the eruption of Chinyero.

Chronological range	Days before eruption	Event	Localities	Maximum Intensity	
1908	March				
	23	-605	One earthquake.	LO	II-III (FM)
	26	-602	Two earthquakes.	LO	V(M)
1908	July				
	23	-483	One small earthquake.	LO	
	25	-481	One small earthquake.	V	
	26	-480	One small earthquake.	PC	
	27	-479	Two earthquakes in La Orotava (IV and VII). One small earthquake felt in Puerto de la Cruz during 3 s.	LO, PC	VII (FM)
	28	-478	One medium-strong earthquake during 3 s. Repeated again 10 minutes later but smaller and shorter. Two small earthquakes 1 h later.	LO	
1908	August				
	4	-471	One strong earthquake.	IC	
1908	September				
	9	-435	One small earthquake.	LR	
1908	November				
	4	-379	Short earthquake with loud underground noise.	LR	
	17	-366	One strong earthquake and three smaller. Some people count 10 or 12 earthquakes during the night in Los Realejos. Many earthquakes felt in La Orotava: V, V, V, III, IV, IV (Forel-Mercalli).	LR, LO	V (FM)
	18	-365	Many earthquakes: V, V, V, III, IV, IV (Forel-Mercalli).	LO	V (FM)
	24	-359	One small earthquake.	LR	
	30	-353	One small earthquake.	LR	
1908	December				
	8	-345	Three earthquakes: small, medium and strong.	MAV	
	19	-334	One earthquake felt in Puerto de la Cruz (V) and Los Realejos (strong). One earthquake felt 20 m later in La Orotava (VI). One earthquake 40 m later in Puerto de la Cruz (V to VI).	PC, LR, LO	VI (FM)
1909	January				
	4	-318	Long and strong earthquake (12 s) felt in La Laguna, Icod and Santa Cruz. Strong movement of the furniture, doors and windows. Great fear among the population. VI (Rossi-Torel).	LL, IC, LR, SC	VI (RT)
	5	-317	One strong earthquake felt in Santa Cruz followed by another one smaller. One strong earthquake felt 1 h later in La Paz and La Orotava during 6 s (VI, Rossi-Foret). Strong movement of the furniture. Great fear among the population. Many people leave La Orotava.	SC, LP, LO	VI (RF)
	8	-314	One small earthquake.		
	9	-313	One small earthquake.		
1909	March				
	19	-244	One strong earthquake.	LR	
	21	-242	Two small earthquakes (3 s) with underground noise.	LO	
1909	April				
	4	-228	One small earthquake.	LR	
	7	-225	One small earthquake.	LR	
	18	-214	One small earthquake with loud underground noise.	LR	

1909	26	-206	One small earthquake.	LR	
	May				
	21	-181	Two small earthquakes of 3 s each (III-IV).	LO	IV (FM)
	24	-178	One or two earthquakes with loud underground noise.	LO	IV-V (FM)
	25	-177	Three strong earthquakes. The population left the houses. Small damages in some houses. Some collapses in cliffs.	LR	
	27	-175	One small earthquake.	LR	
	28	-174	One small earthquake.	LR	
1909	June				
	19	-152	One earthquake very long. Many cracks in the buildings. Stronger damages in the oldest buildings. One earthquake very small (1 s) felt 1 h later.	IC, LO	IV-V (FM)
1909	July				
	6	-135	One short earthquake.	LR	
1909	September				
	23	-56	Two earthquakes of 2 s. Buildings and trees shaken.	LP	VI (FM); VI-VII (MM)
1909	October				
	4	-45	One small earthquake.	LR	
	6	-43	Two earthquakes, the second one small.	LR	
	9	-40	One small earthquake.	LR	
	10	-39	One long earthquake.	LR	
	11	-38	One earthquake.	LR	
	13	-36	One small earthquake.	LR	
1909	November				
	13	-5	One small earthquake.	LR	
	14	-4	Two earthquakes, the first one strong, followed by three or five small earthquakes (felt in Los Realejos). Panic-stricken people. Two strong earthquakes followed by others smaller felt in Santiago del Teide (ground and walls shaken). Two earthquakes followed by more than 20 small shakes felt in Icod; great fear among the population.	LR, ST, IC, CA	V-VI (FM); VII (MM)
	15	-3	Two earthquakes, the second one small, felt in Los Realejos. Two small earthquakes followed by another one strong felt in Icod. Continuous shaking in Icod until the eruption.	LR, IC, CA	
	17	-1	One strong earthquake felt in Caraveo. Continuous shaking.	LR, CA	
	18	0	One strong earthquake felt in Los Realejos. Continuous underground noise and shaking. One strong earthquake (almost as the June 19th earthquake) felt in Icod immediately followed by the eruption. CHINYERO ERUPTION . Panic-stricken people because of the volcano; nearest village abandoned.	LR, IC	
1910	June				
	28	222	End CHINYERO ERUPTION.		

LO, La Orotava; V, Vilaflor; PC, Puerto de la Cruz; IC, Icod; LR, Los Realejos; MAV, Montaña Alta Vista; LL, La Laguna; SC, Santa Cruz; LP, La Paz; ST, Santiago del Teide; CA, Caraveo. M, Mercalli; MM, Modified Mercalli; FM, Forel-Mercalli; RT, Rossi-Torel; RF, Rossi-Foret (Supplementary Figure 2).

Albert, Costa and Martí. Supplementary Figure 1. (.eps)

Albert, Costa and Martí. Supplementary Figure 2. (.eps)

